

Research

Bilateral Trade in Sri Lanka Under Generalized System of Preference(GSP)

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Abstract: The major objective of this thesis is to examine the impact of GSP on the Sri Lankan export sector. Trade data come from the Report of Central Bank Sri Lanka dataset and cover all the available bilateral exports between 25 top export countries over the period 1985 – 2005. Overall, markets receive at least 83% of Sri Lanka's exports. The estimation covers 25 countries with one dependent variable and 16 explanatory variables and all variables are expressed natural logarithm. Trade values are reported in millions of dollars. Population, GDP, REER, and Land Size data have been obtained from a standard source, The World Bank 's World Development Indicators. The study used CEPII data for the country-specific variable: distance. The GDP of Sri Lanka and its trading partners, Population of the provider countries, had a positive influence on Sri Lankan's exports.

These results had a positive impact on Sri Lanka's GDP exports, which resulted in higher returns. The results also suggested that Sri Lankan exports were positively influenced by an increase in GDP in the providers' countries; the higher the income in providers' country, the greater the volume of Sri Lankan exports. The distance, REER and Land variables between Sri Lanka and the providers' countries had its expected sign. The GSP variable is highly significant and positive. This implies that the providers' country that has GSP with Sri Lanka can affect Sri Lanka's exports.

Keywords: GSP, GDP, Sri Lanka and Exports

Introduction

According to historical evidence, Sri Lanka has long been a center for international trade from the pre-historic period to today (GEIGER, 1912). It was an essentially agricultural economy at the time it became an independent nation with the majority of people engaged in agriculture and the greater part of national production and exports derived from agriculture. According to Economic and Social Development of Ceylon 1926 - 1950 issued by the Ministry of Finance in 1948 for instance, agricultural production accounted for 54% of the gross national product and nearly

entirely of the country's exports. Agricultural production, however, was geared mainly to markets of the metropolitan power, as in a typical colonial economy. Thus, the products needed by the metropolitan country, the United Kingdom, such as tea, rubber, coconut products, and spices, were developed whereas products that could easily be grown in the country to meet the needs of the indigenous population were neglected. These export crops were developed mainly with the British capital which also pioneered banking, insurance and export-imports trade at the same time.

The economic history of the past seventies has been two stages of this transformation. From independence to the end of the seventies, the government played an active role in the economy by investing heavily in all sectors of the economy. In the second phase which started in 1977, the interventionist role of the State was attenuated, and private enterprise was encouraged with tax concessions and other incentives including export processing zones in accordance with the global liberalization trends.

Today, we are living in a world driven by ICT (Information and Computer Technology) plus an open and highly competitive market. Therefore, Sri Lanka has to engage in several trade agreements to face high competition in the global world. Froning (2000) explained that a way to do trade agreements is so competitive. In his view, trade agreements promote innovation and competition, they generate economic growth and disseminate democratic values while fostering economic freedom.

Currently, Sri Lanka engages in several, Multilateral, regional and Bilateral trade agreements, and concessions. Such as South Asia Preferential Trade Arrangement (SAPTA), Indo Sri Lanka Free Trade Agreement (ISFTA) and Generalized System of Preferences (GSP). So far, 13 national GSP schemes have been notified to the UNCTAD Secretariat. The following countries offer GSP preferences: Australia, Belarus, Bulgaria, Canada, Estonia, European Union, Japan, New Zealand, Norway, Russian Federation, Switzerland, Turkey and the United States.

This research focuses on the Generalized Trade Agreements of Sri Lanka and how they contribute to enhancing exports in Sri Lanka. According to the world trade organization, today Sri Lanka enjoys the following GSP schemes,

Table 1: GSP in Sri Lanka

Name	Provider(s)	Initial Entry into Force
1. Generalized System of Preferences – Canada (UNCTAD, 2013a)	Canada	7/1/1974
2. Generalized System of Preferences - European Union(UNCTAD, 2010a)	European Union	7/1/1971
3. Generalized System of Preferences – Japan (UNCTAD, 2013b)	Japan	8/1/1971
4. Generalized System of Preferences - New Zealand (UNCTAD, 1999a)	New Zealand	1/1/1972
5. Generalized System of Preferences – Norway (UNCTAD, 2010b)	Norway	10/1/1971
6. Generalized System of Preferences - Russian Federation, Belarus, Kazakhstan	Belarus; Kazakhstan; Russian Federation	1/1/2010
7. Generalized System of Preferences – Switzerland (UNCTAD, 1999b)	Switzerland	3/1/1972
8. Generalized System of Preferences – Turkey (UNCTAD, 2013c)	Turkey	1/1/2002
9. Generalized System of Preferences - United States (UNCTAD, 2003)	United States	1/1/1976

Source: Compiled by author viewing WTO PTA database

The major objective of this study is to examine the impact of GSP on the Sri Lankan export sector. The following specific objectives are expected to be achieved: To identify the factors affecting Sri Lanka exports, to analyze the impact of GSP on economic growth and to identify policy recommendations that improve the exports in Sri Lanka based on the empirical findings.

Materials and methods

In the international context, some literature supported the positive impact of the GSP, and this also had a critical influence on the national economy, while others emphasized the negative impact on the beneficiary. Therefore, the impact of the GSP program on the welfare of the country has two sides. Cooper, Robinson, and Patall (2006) emphasized the positive and negative effects of GSP in the beneficiary countries. He noted the positive impact of GSP programs, since low-cost means of providing economic assistance to developing countries and stimulating trade in the private sector stimulate economic development more effectively than state aid or support. Also, some empirical studies have shown that GSP had a positive effect on increasing exports and created new business opportunities. However, the origin rule (ROO) adversely affected the above advantages. Besides, GSP leads to trade, ranging from more efficient products (with a more competitive

advantage) to less efficient products (with a less competitive advantage) in the beneficiary countries. Therefore, according to Cooper, tariff preferences can stimulate the export of goods for which the country does not have a comparative advantage, which distorts the internal distribution of resources. By diverting resources from potentially influential producers, preferences can reduce exports and growth over time. Although the costs associated with trade diversion are real, empirical evidence suggests that trade diversion of the GSP is small.

The lack of interconnection in GSP programs also contributes to the long-term costs of the beneficiary countries. However, within the framework of the GSP, a protectionist policy was carried out related to import-substituting trade in order to prevent a decrease in mutual exchange tariffs, which impeded long-term growth. Cooper also said that most economists prefer non-discriminatory tariff cuts. GSP-based preferential tariffs can lead to inefficient production and trade patterns. As promiscuous tariffs fall, countries tend to produce and export based on comparative advantage. That is, one country exports products that produce it relatively efficiently, and imports products that other countries produce relatively efficiently. Multilateral tariff reductions, such as those agreed during the GATT Uruguay Round, will redistribute the benefits of trade liberalization in developing countries. While some exporters make a profit when faced with tariff reductions in developed countries, other exporters suffer from a reduction in their preferred preferences under the GSP.

Nevertheless, some literary materials emphasize the positive aspects of GSP programs without taking into account the negative consequences. Baldwin and Murray (1977) used a partial equilibrium system to calculate trade income from the US, EU, and Japanese GSP programs with or without MFN tariff reductions (most profitable countries). Studies have shown that developing countries will benefit from GSP by lowering MFN tariffs. Pomfret (1986) said that export differentiation could be partially balanced and more beneficial for GSP beneficiaries without lowering MFN tariffs.

Kunpanidchakul (2007) examined the impact of GSP programs on the welfare of small countries. On the other hand, research has shown that small countries benefit from the GSP program when political pressure is low. Besides, GSP provides the nation with the benefits of the GSP program and improves overall well-being.

Some publications claim that the GSP program does not benefit its beneficiaries. Ozden and Reinhardt (2005) examined the best ways to integrate developing countries into the global trade

system and reduce their trade barriers. According to research, this harms trade liberalization in recipient countries. They explained that one of the dominant views supports "specific and different approaches to LDC" through programs such as GSP. However, this document provides strong empirical evidence of such programs, and thus our results clearly show that (a) defending GSP rights makes the country less likely to liberalize its trade policies, and (b) that means " a dose of GSP, i.e. a large export dependence on US preferences. The GSP strengthens the country's resistance to liberalization. This result is very reliable.

Panagaria (2002) explains the adverse effects of GSP programs, as well as their impact on recipient liberalization. According to the original concept, he argues that the preference for the GSP must include all goods, not discriminatory in all developing countries, except discrimination in favour of the least developed countries, and exclude mutual concessions from developing countries. Nevertheless, sometimes GSP is limited to many products that have a comparative advantage in developing countries, especially in the textile and clothing industry. Besides, discrimination in developing countries, except those which benefit less developed countries, has also become a feature of current preferential treatment. In GSP, this is achieved by removing countries from the products where they succeed, as well as by using side conditions. Then the other point is the side condition. Panagaria also emphasized that with all specific agendas related to labour, the environment, drug production and trade-related to the provisions of any significant preferences in the GSP framework, these preferences can hardly be considered mutually beneficial or even non-negotiable. Also, these additional conditions create an element of uncertainty for exporters: profits can be withdrawn at any time on the pretext that certain standards are not met. For example, in the United States, local lobbies use these conditions for free to reach their favourite destinations. For example, in April 1992, the United States revoked USP's export rights of \$ 60 million on the pretext that the country did not have adequate intellectual property protection.

Aiello and Demaria (2009) investigated the impact of the EU GSP on developing countries that are eligible for this preferential treatment. According to their findings, the EU GSP has a positive and significant impact on agricultural exports to selected countries. They also stated that after replacing the preference field for each agreement with an index designed to take into account the overall effect of the EU preferential trade policy, it could be argued in this document that the entire EU trade preference system is beneficial for countries that qualify. For the preferential GSP regime. Although sector-level evidence is far more diverse than when combined, traditional GSP

impacts are favourable for many agricultural sectors, showing that EU trade preferences help recipient countries increase their exports.

Frazer, Biesebroeck, and Frazer (2007) studied the AGOA scheme, the US trade preference scheme for African countries, and found a strong positive and significant effect of AGOA on US imports from AGOA countries. They were receiving AGOA increased US imports by an average of 13%. Imports of clothing, agricultural products, minerals, petroleum products and industrial goods each increased by 42%, 8%, 16.6%, 73.5% and 14.6%.

Gil-Pareja, Llorca-Vivero and Martínez-Serrano (2015) provide evidence of export incentives for trade preferences for developing countries. They found a 91% effect in the regression that included short-term. Using the Heckman approach, they calculated the effect of trade preferences by 39%, and with the help of PPML, they found the effect of trade preferences on DC exports by 27%.

Finally, in an international context, together with the results of Gil Paleja Ter et al. (2015) found that average trade preferences are given by EU countries significantly increased exports to developing countries. In particular, they enjoyed the taste of trade, collectively increased their LDCs exports by about 6% and cancelled tariffs by 100%, increased the export of all their products by an average of 6%, and their tariff rates amounted to 1%. It was increased. LDC exports will increase by about 0.3%.

Grossman and Sykes (2005) concluded that fire does not deserve a candle. Little supports the assumption that the GSP scheme has a significant positive effect on the welfare of recipients. Taking the EU scheme as an example, she distinguishes between products that are insensitive, half-high, sensitive and very sensitive. Of course, the interest of most developing countries in exports is concentrated in very detailed product categories.

Dean and Vainio (2013) discuss their impact on U.S. GSP beneficiaries, where high utilization is the non-agricultural preferential margin (lower preferences are a direct result of low US MFN tariffs). The conclusion is that the facts of agriculture should not be hidden; there are several products. Dean and Vainio argue that this is mainly due to product exceptions that face high tariffs from the GSP scheme. Their data confirms the view that the United States is more generous with partners in the Preferential Trade Agreement (PTA) than GSP beneficiaries.

Jean and Kandau (2005) concluded that the EU GSP scheme is significant for sub-Saharan LDCs but less important for South Asian LDCs. Similarly, Kowalski (2005) points to the fact that the impact of Canadian preferences on welfare is minimal for developing countries. Lippoldt (2006)

concludes that Australia's GSP scheme has specific positive effects only in developing countries that are geographically close to donors.

Sachs and Warner (1995) show that developing countries with more liberal trade policies achieve higher levels of growth and development than more protectionist countries. Trefler (2004) shows how tariff cuts can increase industrial productivity in countries that make such cuts.

Tokarik (2006) explores import protection issues in 26 developing countries. Since the samples vary widely, they represent a wide variation in all developing countries, including Argentina, Brazil, Botswana, Malawi, China, India, Albania and Romania. The main goal is to measure the degree of import protection function as a tax in the country's export sector. This is true, and the sample reaches a significant tax rate of 12% in 26 countries.

Mostashari (2010) shows that lowering the tariffs of exporting countries to the US market is more important than calculating a reduction in US import tariffs to explain the success they are using. The GSP scheme has become a kind of wicked version of Jevons' paradox: preferences were supposed to help beneficiaries switch to non-recipient status, but instead, beneficiaries would be rewarded with “Absorbed”, used more often than before (or as long as they could) and never finished. Countries that have come out of this vicious circle are countries that have liberalized and benefited from trade, and that is what Korea has done.

Sachs and Warner (1995) argue that preferred countries will benefit in the short term because GSP recipients mainly import intermediate contributions from GSP providers. They also say that trade preferences will have a distorting effect on LDCs in the long run if strict or detailed rules of origin encourage developing countries to export at MFN tariffs rather than GSP underlined.

Generalized System of Preference (GSP) is a non-reciprocal trade agreement that beneficiaries utilize to enhance their exports. Figure 1 shows that how GSP works in export system of a country with its objectives. First GSP increases exports of a country via reducing tariff from the beneficiary. However, exporters need to increase their comparative advantage while using these GSP facilities because most of the developing countries face cost or price disadvantage and those issues lead to find potential market for their products. So, when they get these benefits, they have also focused to increase their productivity and competitiveness. If they successfully get the real advantage from the GSP, then producers can enhance trade flows even without having GSP facilities later. Figure two, conceptual framework was developed based on Mid-term Evaluation of the EU's Generalised System of Preferences by Gasiorek et al. (2010) or CARIS (2010). They

generalize the gravity equation in order to explain economic development bilateral trade and FDI outward stocks between countries.

Figure 1: Background of Conceptual Framework of the Study

Source: Compiled by the author

Caris(2010) evaluated the impact of the unilateral preferences given by the EU on trade and FDI.

The specification of the gravity model is the following:

$$\ln X_{ijt} = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln pop_{it} + \beta_2 \ln pop_{jt} + \beta_3 \ln Y_{it} + \beta_4 \ln Y_{jt} + \beta_5 \ln dist_{ij} + \beta_6 bord_{ij} + \beta_7 comlang_{ij} + \beta_8 landlocked_j + \beta_9 landlocked_i + \beta_{10} landarea_j + \beta_{11} landarea_i + \beta_{12} colony_{ij} + \sum_n \gamma_n RTA_{ijt}^n + \sum_m \delta_m GSP_{ijt}^m + \sum_r \phi_r year^t + v_i + \xi_j + \zeta_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ijt}$$

The equation was not entirely appropriate in Sri Lanka. There were some adjustments. Borders, landlocked, RTA and LAN 1 were not there. But Real Effective Exchange Rate (REER) was there. Why were borders, landlocked, RTA and LAN 1 were lacking in this thesis? Because Sri Lanka is

an island nation. There are no borders and it is not landlocked. RTA (Regional Trade Agreement) is in the WTO, regional trade agreements (RTAs) are defined as reciprocal trade agreements between two or more partners. They include free trade agreements and customs unions. So, in Sri Lanka, South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA) is the RTA. Also, it is an FTA. However, Sri Lanka has developed FTA India and Pakistan. So, FTA is unnecessary for this thesis.

Therefore, based on this background figure 2 shows the conceptual framework of this study.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

Source: Compiled by the author

Data Sources

Trade data come from the Report of Central Bank Sri Lanka dataset and cover all the available bilateral exports between 25 top export countries over the period 1985 – 2005 (country list in

appendix 1). Overall, markets receive at least 83% of Sri Lanka's exports. The estimation covers 25 countries with one dependent variable and 08 explanatory variables (a total of observations = 800, N = 25 and Time = 32) and all variables expressed natural logarithm. Trade values are reported in millions of dollars. Population, GDP, REER, and Land Size data have been obtained from a standard source, The World Bank 's World Development Indicators. The study used CEPII data (<http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/cepii/cepii.asp>) for the country-specific variable: distance. Absolute distance data refers to the distance between the capitals of each pair of countries in kilometers. The list of GSP entered force before August 2017 has been derived from the Department of Commerce web site.

Model

This model is used to analyze GSP status with main 25 trade exporters of Sri Lanka (country list in the appendix 2). As said above, this analysis, all variables are expressed raw level. According to that data, following equation is constructed:

Equation 1

$$\ln Ex = \ln \alpha + \beta_1 \ln GDPB + \beta_2 \ln GDPP + \beta_3 \ln POPB + \beta_4 \ln POPP + \beta_7 \ln REER + \beta_5 \ln DIST + \beta_6 \ln LAND + \beta_8 GSP$$

Variables

- B is the GSP beneficiary / Exporter
- P is the GSP provider / Importer
- Ex is the value of exports to j from i in the million US dollars
- GDPB ,GDPP is the current GDP at time t; in the million US dollars
- POPP ,POPB is population at time ;
- DIST is the distance between Colombo and GSP provider's capital city;;
- LAND is the area of the country;
- REER is the Real effective exchange rate index (2010 = 100)

- GSP is a dummy variable for all the generalized systems of preferences since the 1970s. Each of this dummy, takes the value of one when I export to j and i received trade preferences from j, otherwise the value of zero.

Conclusion

This section shows the descriptive statistics of dependent and independent variables - employed in this thesis for the top 25 export countries to Sri Lanka. The dependent variables used in the study was export while the independent variables were Provider GDP, Beneficiary GDP, Provider Population, Beneficiary Population, Distance, Land Size, REER and Generalized System of Preference (GSP). Thus, the total observations for each dependent and explanatory variable were 800 (panel data of 25 countries for 32 years). The Table 4.1 presents the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values for the dependent and independent variables.

According to Table 2, the variables comprised 800 observations which are GDPB, POPP, POPB, LAND and DIST. But GSP and EX included 771 observations, GDPP comprised 780 and REER contained 567 observations. Here, dependent variable of this thesis is the: Beneficiary Exports over last 32 years. For the total sample, the mean of exports was 4.292662 with a minimum of zero (zero means Israel was zero over 1985 – 2005 which no accurate information) a maximum of 7.940940 which was the United States of America. The standard deviation statistics for exports was 0.079645 which indicates that the export variation between the top 25 export countries were small.

Correlation Analysis: Table 3 presents the correlation coefficient between the dependent variables and independent variables. According to Table 3 Provider GDP, Beneficiary GDP, Provider Population, Beneficiary Population, Distance, REER, and Generalized System of Preference (GSP) were positively correlated with Beneficiary Export. This clearly shows that Provider GDP, Beneficiary GDP, Provider Population, Beneficiary Population, Distance, REER, and Generalized System of Preference (GSP) increase, the Beneficiary Export moves in same directions. On the other hand, Land Size was negatively correlated with Beneficiary Export. These correlations clearly show that Land size decrease, the Beneficiary Export moves in opposite directions.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	EX	GDPP	GDPB	POPP
Mean	4.292662	12.87065	9.904630	17.36826
Median	4.276666	12.93745	9.684128	17.85142
Maximum	7.940940	16.73701	11.30617	21.04438
Minimum	0.000000	4.845407	8.695918	12.15287
Std. Dev.	1.338582	1.924793	0.839365	1.815982
Skewness	0.092034	-1.256874	0.353358	-0.323780
Kurtosis	3.218417	6.289128	1.872727	3.525996
Jarque-Bera	2.620997	556.9620	59.00642	23.20016
Probability	0.269686	0.000000	0.000000	0.000009
Sum	3309.642	10039.11	7923.704	13894.61
Sum Sq. Dev.	1379.687	2886.062	562.9224	2634.935
Observations	771	780	800	800

	POPB	REER	LAND	DIST	GSP
Mean	16.74054	4.596749	12.48350	8.635726	0.465000
Median	16.74542	4.605170	12.81230	8.791324	0.000000
Maximum	16.86965	5.423118	16.61218	9.746896	1.000000
Minimum	16.57748	3.853759	5.703782	6.649197	0.000000
Std. Dev.	0.079645	0.176303	2.976235	0.665149	0.499086
Skewness	-0.318204	0.288518	-0.728927	-0.959919	0.140344
Kurtosis	2.173392	8.209485	2.829718	4.365165	1.019697
Jarque-Bera	36.27651	649.0189	71.81120	184.9818	133.3463
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	13392.43	2606.357	9986.803	6908.581	372.0000
Sum Sq. Dev.	5.068361	17.59284	7077.524	353.4958	199.0200
Observations	800	567	800	800	800

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Before conducting further into panel data econometric procedures, the diagnostic tests were undertaken to ensure that the data fits the basic assumption of the classical linear regression model. Test of the CLRM assumptions could be presented as follows.

Multicollinearity Test: The correlation matrix in Table 4 below shows the level of correlation of each independent variable. What can be observed from the tables is that, the correlation among the explanatory variables was less than 0.80. This implies there is no higher correlation among the independent variables. That means there is no multicollinearity problem.

Autocorrelation: This study used the dL and du values for 200 observations as approximation of 544 observations. As per the DW table for 200 observations with 12 explanatory variables at 5% level of significance, the dL and du values are 1.643 and 1.896 respectively. In this study, Table 4.4 below shows the Durbin Watson test statistic values of 2.24 model. This Durbin-Watson test statistics reveals that both export model produced values greater than 2.15 but less than 2.49, which

is an indication that export model lies in the inconclusive region where the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation can neither be rejected nor not rejected.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis

	EX	GDPP	GDPB	POPP
EX	1.000000			
GDPP	0.642709	1.000000		
GDPB	0.504063	0.377029	1.000000	
POPP	0.137839	0.658630	0.043645	1.000000
POPB	0.505447	0.378768	0.965004	0.050257
REER	0.148127	0.111502	-0.043178	0.045885
LAND	-0.016831	0.396201	-0.025714	0.663328
DIST	0.187333	0.431671	-0.106733	0.261261
GSP	0.435741	0.483227	-0.056553	0.001379

	POPB	REER	LAND	DIST	GSP
EX					
GDPP					
GDPB					
POPP					
POPB	1.000000				
REER	-0.092432	1.000000			
LAND	-0.017865	-0.108737	1.000000		
DIST	-0.100555	-0.115253	0.435768	1.000000	
GSP	-0.060567	0.088784	-0.136043	0.469997	1.000000

Source: Compiled by author using data from the survey

Table 4: Multicollinearity Test

	GDPP	GDPB	POPP	POPB
GDPP	1.000000			
GDPB	0.400903	1.000000		
POPP	0.687680	0.080454	1.000000	
POPB	0.400960	0.964574	0.084255	1.000000
REER	0.089479	-0.049360	0.029854	-0.096680
LAND	0.434494	0.004310	0.682043	0.009399
DIST	0.442187	-0.088979	0.281498	-0.083883
GSP	0.515671	-0.024794	0.062342	-0.031011

	REER	LAND	DIST	GSP
GDPP				
GDPB				
POPP				
POPB				
REER	1.000000			
LAND	-0.116758	1.000000		
DIST	-0.119980	0.447722	1.000000	
GSP	0.075161	-0.081914	0.480964	1.000000

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Table 5: Autocorrelation Test for Export Model

Variable	Export Model	
	Coefficient	Std. Error
GDPP	0.747550	0.064555
GDPB	0.040910	0.163914
POPP	-0.439333	0.049289
POPB	4.808349	1.761496
REER	2.614840	0.212980
LAND	-0.238190	0.021481
DIST	-0.458637	0.104772
GSP	0.327508	0.121988
C	-50.09195	28.20800
No of observations	544	
Adjusted R ²	70.09%	
F-statistic	115.1807	
Durbin-Watson stat	0.117031	

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Test for Normality: Figure 3 presents that the shape of the histogram indicates that the residuals are normally distributed around its mean of zero. As shown in figure 4.2 the histogram in the JB statistic is significant. This means that the p-values given at this figure are higher than 0.05. Therefore, this study does not reject the null of normality at the 5% level. So, this study concludes that residuals are normally distributed and there is no problem of normality on export models.

Unit Root Test: In this study, unit-root test for stationary was applied to evaluate the stationarity of the variables in the model. Table 6 shows the test for stationarity. Findings of this unit root test indicated that Export, GDPP and REER were in 1st and 2nd Difference Stationary and GDPB has only 2nd Difference Stationary. POPB had no unit test therefore it has to dropped in this dataset.

Figure 2: Normally Distributes

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Table 6: Unit Root Test

Variable	LLC Test	ADF - Fisher Chi-square Test
	Null: Unit root (Non-Stationary) Alternative: No unit root (Stationary)	Null: Unit root (Non-Stationary) Alternative: No unit root (Stationary)
Export	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary
GDPP	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary
GDPB	2 nd Difference Stationary	2 nd Difference Stationary
POPP	Level, 1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary
POPB	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary
REER	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary

Variable	PP - Fisher Chi-square Test	Hadri Test
	Null: Unit root (Non-Stationary) Alternative: No unit root (Stationary)	Null: No unit root (Stationary) Alternative: Unit root (Non-Stationary)
Export	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary
GDPP	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary	2 nd Difference Stationary
GDPB	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary
POPP	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary	Non-Stationary
POPB	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary
REER	1 st and 2 nd Difference Stationary	1 st Difference Stationary

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Multiple Regressions: Table 7 contains the estimation results for the pooled, fixed and random effects models. The pooled model does not allow for heterogeneity of cross sections and cross section specific effects are not estimated.

The combined model does not take into account the heterogeneity of the cross sections, and the specific effects of the cross sections are not evaluated. In addition to these problems, the combined model assumes that all cross sections are homogeneous, and it involves one interception and the same parameters in time and in different countries. The results of the combined panel data model are in the second column of table 7. The third column of table 7 contains the model results with fixed effects.

A model with fixed effects allows different and other parameters to differ, and also has heterogeneity. An F test was performed to verify the probability of the data. As can be seen from table 7, the null hypothesis about the equality of individual effects was rejected by the test. This indicates that a model with individual effects is more effective than a combined model.

The results for the random effect model are presented in the last column of table 7. The random effects model assumes that the effects are generated by a certain distribution, so in this case it

differs from the fixed effect model, but she likes the fixed effect model in recognizing the heterogeneity of the country. Recognizing the differences in the countries of this model, it does not precede each effect individually. This prevents the loss of the degree of freedom that occurs in a model with a fixed effect.

To test the null hypothesis that regressors and individual effects do not correlate, a Hausman test was performed. This test can distinguish between fixed and random effects. Failure to reject the null hypothesis implies that the random-effect model is more effective than the fixed-effect model. A model with a fixed effect will be more efficient than a model with a random effect only if the null hypothesis has been rejected.

Table 7 shows the results of the Hausman test, and it is clear that the null hypothesis is rejected, and this implies that country-specific effects correlate with regressors. This means that a model with fixed effects is preferable, and the interpretation of the coefficients in this thesis will focus on fixed effects, since it is the most efficient model. Clearly, in the case of a model with fixed effects, the overall performance of the gravity model seems good with high R^2 values of 91%. Almost all coefficient estimates are very significant with the expected signs. This indicates that the gravity model is suitable for explaining the flows of Sri Lankan exports to its 25 major exporting partners. As can be seen from Table 7, R^2 indicates that approximately 91 percent of the variability in total exports between Sri Lanka and its 25 export trading partners can be explained using a fixed-effects model. The value of the F-criterion indicates that the overall significance of the model is very significant at 5 percent. First, Under GSP providers (USA, EU, Turkey, New Zealand, Japan, Canada, Russia, Norway and Switzerland) has become top partners due to this GSP scheme.

GSP providers mean Sri Lanka enjoys USA, EU, Turkey, New Zealand, Japan, Canada, Russia, Norway and Switzerland's GSP schemes. They have included 61.3 percent share of total export. However, Top export of Sri Lanka has included 83.8 percent share of total export. Out of that 61.3 percent belongs to the GSP providers. Balance part which is 22.5 percent belongs to Non – GSP providers. Therefore, it is reconfirmed that GSP affect Sri Lankan exports and buying behavior of the Top exporters as well.

Table 7: Estimation Results

Variable	Pool Model		Fixed Effects Model		Random Effects Model	
	Coefficient	Std. Error	Coefficient	Std. Error	Coefficient	Std. Error
GDPP	0.737550	0.064555	0.596283	0.072162	0.504797	0.067955
GDPB	0.030910	0.163914	0.256661	0.079805	0.233795	0.079660
POPP	0.299333	0.049289	2.282344	0.273620	0.561647	0.125394
POPB	3.808349	0.21298	4.476332	0.889944	3.5014	0.87868
REER	0.614840	0.212980	0.355393	0.130279	0.501594	0.126454
LAND	0.028190	0.021481	0.066710	0.022059	0.021150	0.020877
DIST	0.088637	0.104772	0.285187	0.107165	0.287059	0.105092
GSP	0.247508	0.121988	0.556336	0.129830	0.358494	0.125345
C	-66.09195	28.20800	-43.78996	14.40541	-57.77301	14.18559
No of observations	544		544		544	
Adjusted R ²	60.09%		91.08%		74.31%	
F-statistic	103.1807		221.6438		197.3864	
Hausman Test			64.551431			

Source: Compiled by author using data from the survey

Table 8: Summary of Regressions Results

Variables	Expected Results	Actual Results
GDP of the GSP provider	Positive	Positive
GDP of the Beneficiary	Positive	Positive
Population of the GSP provider	Positive	Positive
Population of the Beneficiary	Positive	Positive
Real Effective Exchange Rate (REER)	Positive	Positive
Land size of GSP Providers	Positive	Positive
Distance of Capital (GSP Providers)	Negative	Positive
GSP Statues	Positive / Negative	Positive

Source: Compiled by the Author

Also, Tables 6 Estimation Analysis and Table 7 GSP provider and Top Partners of Sri Lanka clearly showed how much magnitude as GSP variable dominated, then identified the factors affecting Sri Lanka exports. Adjusted R² value is 91 percent and F test also provided this model and it is an acceptable model. GDPP, GDPB, POPP, POPB, REER, LAND, DIST and GSP are the factors affecting Sri Lanka exports. Finally, analyze impact of GSP to the economic growth. The expenditure method is a method for calculating gross domestic product (GDP), which totals consumption, investment, government spending and net exports. Specially, the thesis has paid much consideration on exports. Exports represent the value of all goods and other market services provided to the rest of the world. They include the cost of goods, freight, insurance, transportation, travel, royalties, license fees and other services such as communications, construction, financial,

Table 9: GSP providers and Top Partners of Sri Lanka

GSP providers	Share %	Top Partners of Sri Lanka	Share %
United States of America	27.3	United States of America	27.3
EU (EU countries 27 nations however it has become here top exporting countries.			
United Kingdom, Germany, Italy, Belgium and Luxembourg, Netherlands, France)	26	United Kingdom	10.1
Turkey	1.5	India	5.4
New Zealand	-	Germany	4.9
Japan	2.0	Italy	4.2
Canada	1.7	China	2.0
Russia	1.8	Belgium and Luxembourg	3.3
Norway	-	United Arab Emirates	2.3
Switzerland	1.0	Netherlands	2.0
		Japan	2.0
		Russian Federation	1.8
		France	1.5
		Canada	1.7
		Turkey	1.5
		Australia	1.6
		Iran	1.7
		Hong Kong	1.3
		Israel	0.9
		Mexico	1.3
		Iraq	1.1
		Switzerland	1.0
		Bangladesh	1.1
		Saudi Arabia	1.8
		Singapore	1.1
		Maldives	0.9
Total	61.3	Total	83.8

Source: Compiled by author using data from the survey

information, business, personal and government services. If export increases GDP value increases, if export value decreases GDP value decreases. There is a positive relationship between export and GDP.

In this thesis, GSP had a positive coefficient 0.55 and positive influence on Sri Lankan exports. Therefore, GSP and economic growth has a strong impact on each other.

Suggestions for Future Studies: This study aims to examine the relationship between GSP and Export eight variables. As mentioned in the section on limitations, some suggestions can be made for future studies. There are other macroeconomic variables that may affect GSP and GDP. Future studies could employ those omitted variables and fiscal policy impacts, and quarterly or monthly data should be used for those estimations. In addition, structural breaks should be considered in future studies.

Finally, all these results can help the government and policy makers to undertake appropriate measures to improve the performance of the Sri Lankan foreign trade sector. While all of these results are valuable, more research and more Sri Lankan trade data will add more and more to the foreign trade sector.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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